

D2.1 Use case definition and networking requirements for 6G V2X/Digital Twin v1.0

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Acronyms

AD	Automated Driving
ADE	Application Decision Engine
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIF	Application Intelligence Functions
API	Application Programming Interface
AS	Application Server
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CVH	Connected Vehicle Hub
CV	Connected vehicles
CWS	Collision Warning System
DDT	Dynamic Driving Task
HMI	Human Machine Interface
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine learning
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Function
NIF	Network Intelligence Functions
NWDAF	Network Analytics Function
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
PF	Prediction Function
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
ToD	Tele-Operated Driving
ToV	Tele-Operated Vehicle
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
UC	Use case

Executive Summary

The tremendous advances in mobile communications together with the emergence of many Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) services are transforming the world of transportation that was unchangeable for many decades. These services and technologies will make mobility safer, cheaper, greener, and less stressful. However, the deployment of CAM services is facing many technological, economical, and regulatory challenges. Therefore, many projects and standardization taskforces involving the different stakeholders were launched recently to make CAM services mature enough for mass deployment.

In this context, the objective of UNICO - 6GTWINROAD SP1 project is to design beyond-5G technology enablers for boosting the integration of CAM services and automotive digital twins. This will be done by focusing on architectural and algorithmic aspects. To evaluate the performance of the proposed framework, two use cases were selected: QoS prediction for tele-operating driving and digital twin for cooperative perception. In the first use case, some of the designed mechanisms will be shown in TRL 5 demonstration by using the testbed infrastructure provided by project partner. The second use case will evaluate the performance of the most advanced mechanisms using simulation as the required hardware and software for these mechanisms are not yet available.

The two use cases, their functional architecture, their functional and non-functional requirements, and required KPIs are presented in this document.

1 Introduction

The automotive industry is witnessing a paradigm shift from manually driven vehicles to fully automated vehicles. The Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) has defined six driving automation levels (Figure 1) ranging from no automation at level 0 to full automation at level 5 [1]. Human drivers are no longer driving the vehicle at level 3, also called partial automation, but can be requested to take control if emergency situations occur.

Figure 1 SAE levels of automated vehicles [1].

The digital transition towards these automated vehicles is enabled by connected and automated mobility (CAM), where communication – in particular Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication – is a key aspect. This transition would not been possible without the tremendous advances in wireless communication and computing technologies, which are able today to satisfy automotive safety requirements by providing extremely high data rates, low latency, high reliability, and pervasive availability.

One of the key challenges in transforming CAM to commercial reality is the deployment of V2X services over large geographic areas. This is a challenging problem as it requires extremely high reliability and availability with the presence of huge amount of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs). To overcome this challenge, new concepts and technologies must be integrated into the next generation of mobile networks. These networks should be aware of the surrounding environment (in this case, roads and highways) and able to autonomously adapt their configuration to cope with the changes in this environment. This can be done by integrating the concept of integrated context-aware Artificial Intelligence (AI) mechanism in the control plane of future 5G/6G networks. In this context, the objective of 6G-TWINROAD project is to design and evaluate a new control-plane architecture allowing 5G/6G networks to interact with the external environment and automatically change some of its configuration or service configuration.

To reach the objective of automated vehicles, different regulatory and standardization bodies are working together to provide the requirements, architectural concepts, technologies, and use cases [1]-[4]. One of the interesting use cases where the AI integration could be beneficial, is Tele-operated Driving (ToD) where a CAV can be

remotely driven through a mobile radio network in certain situations. In this case, having integrated AI in the control plane will allow the network to predict network problems and provide enough time for the tele-operation driver to take the right decisions. Another interesting use case is the evaluation of cooperative perception at scale, where a big number of vehicles are exchanging CAM messages. Evaluating the performance of the system in such a use case is very challenging as it requires the availability and operation of a huge number of vehicles. For this reason, this use case will be evaluated in a digital twin like simulator that uses realistic road and network traffic data. In summary, the two use cases that will be tested are: Quality of Service (QoS) prediction for Tele-operated driving, and digital twin for cooperative perception.

In this project, we will design, evaluate, and test a context-aware AI-based architecture allowing the network to interact with its environment and the V2X application, and automatically change any parameters to provide seamless and safe experience for vehicle passengers. The IDIADA Connected Vehicle Hub (CVH) will be used to validate the end-to-end performance of the first use case in a realistic environment.

1.1 Deliverable overview

This deliverable is structured as follows. In Section 2 and Section 3, the two use cases are described in detail. In Section 4, the relation to the involved stakeholders is presented and finally, in Section 5, a summary of the topics discussed in the document will be provided.

2 Use Case 1: QoS Prediction for Tele-operated Driving

In Use Case 1 (UC1), we study the impact of predicting changes in the communication QoS provided by the mobile network to the Tele-operated Vehicle (ToV) on the quality of Tele-operated Driving (ToD) experience. The prediction will be performed by a developed entity in the project that notifies the remote driver with the expected degradation in QoS.

2.1 Motivation

In the near future, we will be able to see the dream of replacing the current transportation system that is totally relying on human drivers by fully autonomously driven vehicles for carrying both passengers and cargos. We are already witnessing some trials of Level 4 of autonomous vehicles that can be self-driven in limited areas with the possibility of human overriding. Furthermore, some countries already licensed the use of unmanned Level 4 vehicles such as in Japan and Germany [5][6]. However, a Connected an Autonomous Vehicle (CAV) may encounter a very complex and unexpected situation and it might be able to accomplish its Dynamic Driving ask (DDT) [1]. In this case, the CAV can request a ToD service to be remotely driven until the unhandled situation disappears [7]. For instance, the German Aerospace Center (Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt; DLR) is conducting research to find fast and safe solutions to this situation based on teleoperation [8]. Another situation where ToD can be activated in a connected vehicle is when the driver experiences health issues that might impair his reaction and judgment, or he wants to rest and sleep as in the case of truck drivers who can be driving for long distances. Furthermore, ToD can be used for automated parking; when a vehicle reaches a parking lot, the driver can leave the vehicle that will be parked by a remote driver [7]. The 5GAA has envisaged three-stage progressive deployment roadmap for ToD services in different environments [9]: ToD in confined areas, ToD in dedicated local public roads or areas, and ToD for cross-region mobility.

Even though the availability of mobile networks is extremely high (requirement in 5G is 99.99% [10]), there will be still some regions, although extremely small, where the coverage is not always available due for instance, tunnels, complex orography, and network failure. For most of the services, the small percentage of unavailability (less than 0.01%) can lead to a risky situation in ToD. The same risky situation will appear if latency, reliability, positioning, and data rate requirements are not satisfied. This risky situation may jeopardize the safety of the ToV and the other vehicles on the road if no very responsive measures are available (e.g., stopping the vehicle or activating the autonomous driving operation when available). Some measures are not always available in ToV (e.g., autonomous driving) and others can be very risky at high speed (e.g., stopping the vehicle suddenly). Therefore, predicting such risky situation with enough anticipation will provide the remote driver with enough time to take the best action

(e.g., slow down until reaching a safe area to park before the degradation of QoS, move to the breakdown lane). Therefore, having a QoS predictor and decision-making engine (simply denoted QoS predictor hereafter) integrated in the network will be very appropriate for such scenarios. The QoS predictor will monitor different parameters of the network and the road environment and can notify the remote driver when the QoS prediction is below the minimum required by the ToD service.

The notification of QoS change for V2X application has been already introduced in 3GPP specifications for V2X services. The V2X application can be notified of QoS changes by the Network Exposure Function (NEF) using the Notification on QoS Sustainability Analytics functionality [11]. The latter is provided by the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) [12]. Furthermore, the 5GAA discussed the different aspects and mechanisms to perform QoS prediction in V2X applications [13]. In addition, 5GCroCo consortium deployed a Prediction Function (PF) to change the resolution of the video streaming in the uplink depending on collected measurements such as signal strength and prediction in space and time [14].

As explained above, ToD requires the integration of some QoS prediction mechanisms to guarantee the safety of the vehicle passengers and other vehicles. To provide the best prediction and action, the QoS predictor should be able to use information from network (e.g., cell is down or congested in a given area, QoS is better in 4G than in 5G), and road environment (e.g., road plan, traffic jams, accidents) and vehicle (e.g., speed, position, and direction of the vehicle). By creating a simple **digital twin** combining these three sources of information (see Figure 2), possible QoS degradation due to coverage holes, traffic jams, etc. can be detected and notification can be sent to the Tele-operation Centre (ToC) where the remote driver is performing his tasks.

Figure 2 A simple digital twin of the road network containing the coverage of cells (polygons with different colours), the road plan (the blue lines), the vehicles' positions (dots with different colours), and the position of the ToV (blue vehicle).

2.2 Use case description

In UC1, tele-operated driving is provided to a CAV that is not able to handle given circumstances. The CAV will be moving from region with optimal conditions in 5G network for tele-operation to poor quality region and returning the region with optimal conditions. The QoS change will be predicted by the network in advance to provide a sufficient window of time to take the necessary actions. Based on the type of actions, two scenarios will be tested:

- Scenario 1: the network will force the CAV to connect to another network (3G, 4G) providing the optimal conditions if available. When the QoS requirement is satisfied again with the 5G, the CAV will connect again to the 5G network (Figure 3).

Figure 3 QoS prediction for ToD scenario 1.

- Scenario 2: if no other network can provide the optimal condition, the network will send a notification to the ToC with the predicted QoS. The ToC will translate these requirements to an action that can be 1) reduce the speed to a certain limit, 2) stop the vehicle, or 3) give the control to the driver in the vehicle. When the QoS is optimal again, a new notification will be sent to the ToC to remove the warning (Figure 4).

Figure 4 QoS prediction for ToD scenario 2.

The Human Machine Interface (HMI) in the ToC will show the measured service and network KPIs of the two scenarios.

2.3 Functional architecture

To be able to fulfil the requirements of this use case, the functional architecture depicted in Figure 5. It includes three main layers distributed over three blocks, i.e, mobile network block, the ToV, and the ToC that resides in the Edge. The three layers are: communication layer (in blue), ToD layer (in orange), and QoS prediction layer (in green), which will be developed within this project.

Figure 5 Functional architecture of UC1.

2.3.1 Communication layer

The communication layer incorporates the infrastructure, the ToD Application Server (AS) in the edge, and the multi-technology modem in the ToV:

- The **infrastructure** resides in the mobile network block and enables seamless communication between the ToV and the edge where the ToD application resides. It contains the Radio Access Network (RAN) and core network of four technologies, i.e., 3G, 4G, 5G.
- The **ToD AS** resides in the edge and secures the communication between the ToD application in the edge and the ToD application in the ToV through the infrastructure. It also manages the registration and authentication requests.
- The **multi-technology modem** resides in the ToV and allows the applications inside the ToV to have connectivity through one of the technologies provided by the infrastructure.

2.3.2 ToD layer

The ToD layer incorporates the ToD interface in the edge and the in-vehicle ToD interface:

- The **ToD interface** resides in the edge and contains the required software and hardware (receiving information and data from the in-vehicle ToD app, supporting the environmental perception building process from the ToD operator, performing the driving tasks, and transmitting commands to the in-vehicle App) to provides the ToD functionalities (e.g., HMI, gear, steering wheel, and pedals) from the server side.

- The **in-vehicle ToD interface** resides in the ToV and contains the required software and hardware for collecting and sending sensor and camera data to the ToD interface at the edge, and receiving and executing remote driving commands to provides ToD functionalities (e.g., HMI, actuators, sensors, Lidar, cameras, GNSS) in addition to the Automated Driving (AD) functionality that can be activated in case connection with the ToD interface in the edge is totally lost.

2.3.3 QoS prediction layer

The QoS prediction layer incorporates the Prediction Function (PF) client in the edge and the PF in the mobile network:

- The **PF** resides in the mobile network block and contains the required software and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) required to communicate with the network to collect QoS related data. This data is used by the PF to predict possible QoS degradation and reported to the PF client in the edge. The PF will also have registration and authentication functionalities allowing external function to subscribe to a service, which is in our case *notification of QoS degradation*.
- The **PF client** resides in the edge and is responsible of interacting with the PF to 1) subscribe to the *notification of QoS degradation* service, 2) receive warning notification from the PF and process it, 3) and send the recommendation to the HMI.

2.4 High-level Requirements and KPIs

This section presents the functional and non-functional requirements for the optimal operation of the ToD. Furthermore, it introduces the different KPIs and their target values.

The functional requirements are divided by block: In-Vehicle ToD interface, ToV modem, ToD AS, ToD interface, infrastructure, PF, and PF client whereas the non-functional requirements are presented as quality of the whole UC.

Each requirement will have:

- a unique identifier (ID) using the format ["FR/NFR"- "Block name"- "Number"], where FR/NFR represents Functional or Non-Functional requirements, the block name is 3-letter representation of the block, and the number is a sequential number,
- a short description,
- a priority following the MoSCoW method that divides requirements into four group: MUST have, SHOULD have, COULD have, and WON'T have [15].

2.4.1 Functional requirements

To operate ToD in optimal conditions, the below requirements should be satisfied.

2.4.1.1 In-vehicle ToD interface functional requirements

The functional requirements of the in-vehicle ToD interface are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Functional requirements of the in-vehicle ToD interface.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-VTI-1	The in-vehicle ToD interface must collect reliable information about its environment from its sensors/cameras/Lidar.	MUST
FR-VTI-2	The in-vehicle ToD interface must process the sent commands from the ToC and execute them in real time.	MUST
FR-VTI-3	The in-vehicle ToD interface must establish a connection with the ToD interface and send the collected data.	MUST
FR-VTI-4	The in-vehicle ToD interface must accurately determine its position and speed.	MUST
FR-VTI-5	The in-vehicle ToD interface should be able to go to a minimal risk condition if a malfunction in the ToD occurs.	SHOULD

2.4.1.2 ToV modem functional requirements

The functional requirements of the ToV modem are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Functional requirements of the ToV modem.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-VMO-1	The ToV modem must connect to the ToD AS through the different mobile networks.	MUST
FR-VMO-2	The ToV should collect KPIs related to latency, throughput, interruption time, reliability, and signal levels and send it to the ToC.	SHOULD

2.4.1.3 ToD AS functional requirements

The functional requirements of the ToD AS are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 Functional requirements of the ToD AS.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-TAS-1	The ToD AS must be able to receive and register requests for teleoperating a ToD to a specific location.	MUST
FR-TAS-2	The ToD AS must be able to accept or deny the teleoperation of a ToV to a specific location.	MUST
FR-TAS-3	The ToV must be able to connect to the ToV modem through the different mobile networks.	MUST

2.4.1.4 ToD interface functional requirements

The functional requirements of the ToD interface are listed in Table 4.

Table 4 Functional requirements of the ToD interface.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-TOD-1	The ToD interface must set everything up (particularly at HMI level) for a ToD session start and adapt as it goes.	MUST
FR-TOD-2	The ToD interface must be able to acquire the sent environmental information from the in-vehicle ToD interface and show it in the HMI in real time.	MUST
FR-TOD-3	The ToD interface must be able to send the commands of the remote driver to the in-vehicle ToD interface in real time.	MUST
FR-TOD-4	The ToD must display the notification send by the PF when predicted QoS does not fulfil ToD requirements.	MUST
FR-TOD-5	The ToD interface should be able to display the measured KPIs send by the ToV modem.	SHOULD

2.4.1.5 Infrastructure functional requirements

The functional requirements of the infrastructure are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Functional requirements of the infrastructure for UC1.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-INF-1	The infrastructure must be able to provide seamless and continuous connection between the ToD and ToD operator.	MUST
FR-INF-2	The infrastructure should be able to ensure that the KPIs defined in Table 6 are in the ranges provided in Table 6 [17].	SHOULD

Table 6 KPI definition for UC1 [17].

KPI Name	Unit	Definition
Command Latency	[ms]	Latency between the ToC and ToV while sending tele-operation commands (e.g., speed value, changing direction, etc.). It is one way application layer delay.
Data transfer Latency	[ms]	Latency between the ToV and ToC while sending sensor information (i.e., camera videos, current position, speed, etc.). It is one way application layer delay.
Command Reliability	[%]	Ratio between correctly received command messages packets by the ToV and the packets sent by the ToC.
Data transfer Reliability	[%]	Ratio between correctly received sensor information packets by the ToC and the packets sent by the ToV.
Uplink Service Data-Rate	[Mbps]	Number of correctly received sensor information bits by the ToC within a certain time window.
Downlink Service Data-Rate	[Mbps]	Number of correctly received command messages bits by the ToV within a certain time window.

Table 7 Target KPI values for UC1 [17].

KPI Name	Target value
Command Latency	20-50 ms
Data transfer Latency	100 ms
Command Reliability	99-99.8 %
Data transfer Reliability	95-99 %
Uplink Service Data-Rate	10 - 50 Mbps
Downlink Service Data-Rate	Maximum of 0.5 Mbps

The target values in Table 7 can change based on the measurements that will be done during the tests in IDIADA testbed.

2.4.1.6 PF functional requirements

The functional requirements of the PF are listed in Table 8.

Table 8 Functional requirements of the PF.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-QPF-1	The PF must be able to receive and register requests for subscription to the <i>notification of QoS degradation</i> service.	MUST
FR-QPF-2	The PF must collect QoS-related data from different sources.	MUST
FR-QPF-3	The PF must detect any change in the QoS for certain time periods and certain distance.	MUST
FR-QPF-4	The PF should force the ToV to connect to a network that provides the required QoS in case the QoS provided by the 5G network is not enough.	SHOULD
FR-QPF-5	The PF should send a notification with the predicted QoS to the PF client.	SHOULD

2.4.1.7 PF client functional requirements

The functional requirements of the PF client are listed in Table 9.

Table 9 Functional requirements of the PF client.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-PFC-1	The PF client must be able to subscribe to the <i>notification for QoS degradation service</i> .	MUST
FR-PFC-2	The PF client must be able to process the notification send by the PF when predicted QoS does not fulfil ToD requirements and send it to the HMI.	MUST

2.4.2 Non-functional requirements

The non-functional requirements of UC1 are provided as listed in Table 10.

Table 10 Non-functional requirements of UC1.

ID	Description	Priority
NFR-UC1-1	Availability: the service must be available in the whole project testbed.	MUST
NFR-UC1-2	Continuity: The service must be provided continuously without disruption.	MUST
NFR-UC1-3	Modifiability: The service should be easily modified to add new features.	SHOULD
NFR-UC1-4	Isolation: The service should be isolated from other services running in the testbed.	SHOULD
NFR-UC1-5	Performance: The service should be able to detect QoS degradation with enough time to adapt the system.	SHOULD
NFR-UC1-6	Adaptability: The service should be provided whatever mobile network technology is available.	SHOULD

3 Use Case 2: Digital twin for cooperative perception

In Use Case 2 (UC2), we study the impact of deploying cooperative perception at scale (i.e., assuming all vehicles are connected vehicles and sharing messages) on network performance and how to enable the network to adapt to this new load. To do this, we will design and emulate a context-aware Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN)-based architecture with integrated Machine Learning (ML) algorithms for load balancing.

3.1 Motivation

Cooperative perception enables Connected Vehicles (CVs) to exchange their sensor/cameras/LiDAR information with each other and with the infrastructure. It extends CVs detection capabilities to detect obstructing objects (e.g., other vehicles, obstacles, pedestrians) beyond their local sensing capabilities and thus facilitating future deployment of CAVs. The sensor information is exchanged using V2X messages such as Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) and Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENM) [16].

However, most innovation studies [17]-[21] either use a very limited number of CVs (e.g., 2 or 3) or do not use real data. Therefore, the results obtained can only be valid for early deployment of cooperative perception where very few vehicles will be using V2X communications.

In the future, CVs will be much more available on the roads and will lead to a significant increase of network load in beyond 5G networks. To cope with this significant load, which is related to road safety in most of the cases, one idea could be to assign a specific network slice [22] to V2X communication to guarantee its requirements. In addition, network resources should be managed in a way that the requirements are either fulfilled or the application function responsible for the road safety (e.g., Collision Warning System – CWS) must be notified so it can take corrective actions.

In this context, this use case will be used to study the performance of the O-RAN based architecture that enables the optimization of the usage of network resources in case of mass deployment of CV. As such architecture is not yet supported by mobile network manufacturers, the evaluation will be done using simulation, i.e. **digital twin**. The novelty of this digital twin is the use of realistic data for road traffic [23] or real network traffic generated in task T3.1 of this project.

3.2 Use case description

In UC2, CAM messages will be sent by each vehicle considered in the scenario to the V2X AF with a period T . Each CAM message received by the V2X AF will be forwarded to all vehicles in a given area surrounding the sending vehicle. Therefore, for each message sent in the uplink, M messages will be sent in the downlink (The value of M depends on

vehicular density). Hence, the downlink will be more congested than the uplink and this why we only study the downlink in this use case.

Two scenarios will be considered in this use case:

- Cologne scenario extracted from the Tapas dataset [23]. In this scenario, shown in Figure 6, the vehicular traffic is obtained from the dataset and the network traffic is generated assuming all vehicles are sending their CAM messages periodically.
- Network-based dataset extracted from network KPI dataset generated in Task T3.1. In this scenario, the utilised resources in the network are available and will be mapped to CAM messages.

Figure 6 Cologne scenario for use case 2.

In both scenarios, cells will be experiencing significant load variation. For a better understanding, Figure 7 presents such load variation between two neighbouring cells shown in Figure 6 (BS3 and BS4). When the network detects the overload of BS3, it will try to offload some of this load to neighbouring base stations (e.g., BS4) that have unused resources using the load balancing algorithm that will be developed. In case the load balancing algorithm does not provide a solution that removes all existing overload, the V2X AF will be notified and will take the necessary actions, which is to reduce the frequency of sending DENM messages. To provide a coordinated response to select the best overload mitigation approach, this algorithm will use historical information collected from previous days and the actual status of the network.

Figure 7 Example of cell load in Tapas scenario.

3.3 Functional architecture

The functional architecture depicted in Figure 8 is designed to fulfil the requirements of this use case. It includes three main layers distributed over three blocks, i.e., mobile network block, the CV, and the Application Server (AS) that resides at the edge. The three layers are: communication layer (in blue), V2X layer (in orange), and intelligence layer (in green), which will be developed in this project.

Figure 8 Functional architecture of UC2.

3.3.1 Communication layer

The communication layer incorporates the infrastructure, the AS modem, and the CV modem:

- The **infrastructure** resides in the mobile network block and enables the seamless communication between the CVs and the AS. It contains the 5G SA basic network functions such as the gNBs that are connected to RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) that resides in the Network Intelligence Functions (NIF) block, and the legacy core elements excluding the Network Analytics Function (NWDAF).

- The **AS modem** resides in the edge and secures the communication between the V2X protocol stacks in the CV and the AS. It also manages the registration and authentication requests.
- The **CV modem** resides in the CV and allow the applications inside the CV to have connectivity through the 5G network provided by the infrastructure.

3.3.2 Intelligence layer

The layer incorporates the Application Intelligence Functions (AIF) in the AS and the NIF in the mobile network:

- The **NIF** resides in the mobile network block and contains the required Network Functions (NFs), software, and APIs required to adapt the network to changes in traffic demands while efficiently using its resources. It includes the RIC software plug-ins that enable the deployment of AI-based algorithms in the RAN to optimize resource usage. In addition, it includes the context information database where collected data and actions from the RIC are recorded to be used later by the AI algorithms of the RIC. Finally, this layer includes the NWDAF that provides the software and APIs allowing the core network to collect data from network functions, user equipment, and Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (OAM). The collected data is used by the NWDAF as input for 5G analytics to enhance network performance and user experience.
- The **AIF** resides in the AS and is responsible of interacting with the NIF to 1) subscribe to the services provided by the NIF, 2) receive warning notification from the NIF and process it, 3) and send the recommendation to the CV. It includes the Application Decision Engine (ADE) that takes the decisions based on the warning notifications received from the NIF, and the V2X database where all data about the registered CVs are recorded (e.g., location, speed).

3.3.3 V2X layer

The V2X layer incorporates the V2X protocol stacks in the CV and the AS. In this project, the CV V2X stack is responsible for only sending periodically the CAM messages to the AS and receiving the DENM sent by the latter. The V2X stack in the AS is responsible for receiving the CAM messages from the registered CVs and forwarding each message to all CVs in the vicinity of the source CV (the destination CV will be determined based on the location of the source CV and the registered CVs recorded in the V2X database).

3.4 High level requirements and KPIs

This section presents the functional and non-function requirements for the second use case. Furthermore, it introduces the different KPIs and their target values.

The functional requirements are divided by block: V2X stack, CV modem, AS modem, infrastructure, NIF, and AIF, whereas the non-functional requirements are presented as

quality of the whole UC. The description of the requirements is done in the same way as in UC1.

3.4.1 Functional requirements

In this section, we introduce the functional requirements of UC2.

3.4.1.1 V2X stack functional requirements

The functional requirements of the V2X stack are listed in Table 11.

Table 11 Functional requirements of the V2X stack.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-VXS-1	The CV V2X stack must be able to periodically send the CAM messages to the AS and receive the messages sent through the network from the latter.	MUST
FR-VXS-2	The V2X stack in the AS should be able to receive the CAM messages from the registered CVs and forward each message to all CVs in the vicinity of the source CV.	MUST
FR-VXS-3	The V2X stack in the AS must be able to take the necessary action base on the new policy generated by the AIF.	MUST

3.4.1.2 CV modem functional requirements

The functional requirements of the CV modem are listed in Table 12.

Table 12 Functional requirements of the CV modem.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-CVM-1	The CV modem must connect to the AS modem through the 5G network.	MUST

3.4.1.3 AS modem functional requirements

The functional requirements of the AS modem are listed in Table 13.

Table 13 Functional requirements of the AS modem.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-ASM-1	The AS modem must be able to connect to the CV modem through the 5G network.	MUST

3.4.1.4 Infrastructure functional requirements

The functional requirements of the infrastructure are listed in Table 14.

Table 14 Functional requirements of the infrastructure for UC2.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-NET-3	The infrastructure must be able to provide seamless and continuous connection between the CV and the AS.	MUST
FR-NET-4	The infrastructure should be able to ensure that the KPIs defined in Table 15 are in the ranges provided in Table 16.	SHOULD

Table 15 KPI definition for UC2.

KPI Name	Unit	Definition
Percentage of used PRBs	[%]	The ratio between the used PRBs in a cell at a given sample to the total number of PRBs in this cell, times 100
Overload time	[s]	The amount of time a particular cell has its percentage of used PRBs above 100. The KPI will be shown as a cumulative distribution function (CDF).
Percentage of delayed CAM packets	[%]-	Percentage of users receiving at least a CAM packet from a neighbouring user with a delay at least twice the maximum allowed CAM interval as defined in [24]. Note that not having a clear position update from a neighbouring user might lead to unsafe driving decisions.

Table 16 Target KPI values for UC2.

KPI Name	Target value
Percentage of used PRBs	The average over all cells is to be minimized and should be always lower than 100.
Overload time	The 95 percentiles should be lower than 5% of the simulated time.
Percentage of delayed CAM packets	It should be lower than 5%.

The target values in Table 16 can change based on the further analysis of the available datasets.

3.4.1.5 NIF functional requirements

The functional requirements of the NIF are listed in Table 17.

Table 17 Functional requirements of the NIF.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-NIF-1	The NIF must be able to receive data from RAN and core and record them in the context information database.	MUST
FR-NIF-2	The NIF should be able to find solution to network congestion using data from context information database.	SHOULD
FR-NIF-3	In case no solution is found for network congestion, the NIF must send notification warning to the AIF	MUST

3.4.1.6 AIF client functional requirements

The functional requirements of the AIF are listed in Table 18.

Table 18 Functional requirements of the AIF.

ID	Description	Priority
FR-AIF-1	The AIF must be able to subscribe to NIF service of warning notification.	MUST
FR-AIF-2	The AIF must be able to receive and process the warning notification from the NIF.	MUST
FR-AIF-3	The NIF must notify the V2X stack of the AS by the decision it takes based on warning notification from the NIF. .	MUST

3.4.2 Non-functional requirements

The non-functional requirements are provided for the whole service of UC2 as listed in Table 19.

Table 19 Non-functional requirements of UC2.

ID	Description	Priority
NFR-UC2-1	Availability: the service must be available in the whole simulated area.	MUST
NFR-UC2-2	Continuity: The service must be provided continuously without disruption.	MUST
NFR-UC2-5	Performance: The service must significantly reduce the delay in receiving CAM messages.	MUST
NFR-UC2-3	Modifiability: The service should be easily modified to add new features.	SHOULD

4 Stakeholders involved

The test of use case 1 in 6G-TWINROAD SP1 project will be carried out with IDIADA Automotive Technology S.A, being responsible for developing the tasks involved in WP4: 6G V2X/Digital Twin Use Case and Technology validations, supporting the development of the use cases. The core objective of WP4 is to validate beyond 5G V2X use cases enabled by the technologies developed in WP3. Particularly, IDIADA's contributions will be distributed in two major tasks:

- **T4.2: Test site preparation and integration of edge components**

In this task, the test site of IDIADA will be prepared and maintained for the execution of the validation plan for use case 1 defined in deliverable D4.1. The following activities are expected to be executed along this task:

- 5G network deployment in the trial site.
- Ensuring the availability of functional ToC and connected ToV that can support the use case.
- Upgrading the on-board unit to support the functionalities required by the use case.
- Edge server deployment.
- Onboarding the components developed by I2CAT in WP3 in the vehicle, the ToC HMI (to show the notification), and the edge.
- Provide access to network KPIs.

The deliverable generated by this task is D4.2 - Testbed setup, and integration of 6G V2X/Digital Twin technologies. It contains the description of the process of preparing the test site and of onboarding the WP3 components.

- **T4.3: Test site execution support**

In this task, IDIADA will support the execution of the validation plan including remote driving the ToV, network configuration (e.g., turning off one technology in a cell), and IT support for 5G network and edge. In addition, IDIADA will support the extraction of the KPIs. The following activities are expected to be executed along this task:

- Setting up and remote driving the ToV.
- Performing network configuration that will be provided in the evaluation plan.
- Providing IT support in case of problems in the network, vehicle, or edge.
- Performance evaluation from the vehicle side for the different use cases.

Two deliverables will be generated by this task. The first one is D4.3 - Validation and execution of the 6G V2X/Digital Twin Test plan. It contains the description of the final testbed deployment including all the blocks defined in the use case description. In addition, it will contain the extracted KPIs that will be specified in the validation plan. The second one is D4.4- 6GTWINROAD-MNO demonstrator.

This deliverable is a video of the executed of the demonstrator of the mechanisms developed in the project and deployed in the test site.

It should be noted that the test of use case 2 in 6G-TWINROAD SP1 project will be carried out by I2CAT using simulation tools. This is due to the fact of the complexity of finding a test site that allows real time configuration of the network.

5 Conclusions

In this document, we presented two use cases to evaluate beyond-5G technologies in realistic environments: Quality of Service (QoS) prediction for Tele-operated driving, and digital twin for cooperative perception. The two use cases are described in detail together with their functional architecture. In addition, the functional and non-functional requirements that need to be fulfilled by the different modules of this architecture are described and the required KPIs are explained with their target values. The first use case will be demonstrated in IDIADA testbed, whereas the second use case will be evaluated using simulation.

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